

COMPETENCY OF MAPEH 6 TEACHERS AND LEARNERS PERFORMANCE: A CORRELATIONAL STUDY

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 24

Issue 4

Pages: 371-380

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2268

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13372904

Manuscript Accepted: 07-23-2024

Competency of MAPEH 6 Teachers and Learners Performance: A Correlational Study

Rosalie D. Magallanes,* Roel P. Villocino
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The main objective of this study was to determine the competency level among MAPEH teachers teaching Music to grade six learners of selected public school of Loreto North District. It utilized the descriptive causal correlational and comparative research design and applied the following statistical tools: mean Pearson – r, independent T-test and Anova. This investigation used a research-made survey questionnaire and summative assessment tool. Universal sampling technique was used to 20 MAPEH teachers and their respective music learners in Grade 6 from selected public elementary schools of Loreto North District. The study's result revealed that most teachers teaching Music to grade six learners ages 39 years and below. Female teachers dominate in the field of teaching. Most of them have less than 9 months of teaching experience. In addition, most teachers teaching music in grade six have less than 19 hours of training/seminar experience. Furthermore, the level of academic performance of grade six learners in music in terms of test scores is fairly satisfactory. Survey revealed that there is a significant relationship between the level of pedagogical competency of MAPEH teachers, the length of teaching experience, and the number of training or seminars attended to the academic performance of Grade six learners. However, there is no significant difference in the level of pedagogy of MAPEH teachers when grouped according to age and sex. As a recommendation, teachers must motivate themselves to grow professionally and develop a sense of responsibility in their competency. Ultimately, teachers must study the curriculum competency-based in Music education and acquire better self-study and learning skills to further develop a sense of responsibility in accomplishing the task provided in the MELC. In the same manner, teachers must engage in providing alternative instructional designs that use developed instructional materials that are based on the needs of the pupils. Most importantly, school heads must provide full support to teachers, especially in conducting seminars or training workshops to enhance the skills of their teachers and purchase in some way musical instruments for teachers and learners to manipulate in the classroom.

Keywords: *competency-based curriculum, competency level, learner academic performance*

Introduction

MAPEH is one of the subjects in the K-12 curriculum, encompassing Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health, and is taught by generalist teachers in elementary schools. Some generalist primary teachers demonstrate negative attitudes towards teaching music (Spruce et al., 2012) due to self-perception of inadequate music knowledge, lack of training, limited teaching experience, and inability to play musical instruments (Welch & Henley, 2014). Teachers play a critical role in student learning and achievement, being the main actors in their classrooms (Saptono, 2023). Their competencies, which include a related set of knowledge, skills, and attitudes, are essential for effective teaching. Competent teachers can provide equivalent instruction to all learners, while those lacking competencies may struggle to deliver the education students deserve.

Consistent findings have been reported in international studies. In Australia, 46% of kindergarten teachers have never learned to play a musical instrument or sing, posing significant challenges in directing musical activities for children (Barrett, Flynn, et al., 2019). In Greece, a study revealed that 75% of 108 early childhood student teachers had no musical training (Koutsoupidou, 2010). In Hong Kong, generalist teachers are resistant and feel embarrassed to sing due to self-perceived inadequacies, often comparing themselves unfavorably to classical performers (Chung, 2022). Similarly, one study in England found that many generalist teachers believed they were not competent to teach music, perceiving themselves as "non-musicians" (Stell, 2020).

Teaching music education in the Philippines can be challenging for teachers for a variety of reasons. According to study, Music education in the Philippines can face a lack of appropriate curricula, a lack of resources and tools, a low budget for music programs, inadequate training for teachers lack of resources and materials, and low teacher compensation. (Philippine Music Festival & Awards Foundation, 2019)

As the District MAPEH Coordinator for Loreto North District from S.Y. 2015-2019, the researcher observed that among the four components of MAPEH, Music consistently had the highest number of least learned competencies at the Grade 6 level, compared to Arts, Physical Education, and Health. At Sto. Tomas Elementary School, where the researcher currently teaches, many colleagues avoid taking on MAPEH as a teaching load due to the inclusion of Music. They believe they lack the skills in reading notes, playing instruments, and have insufficient teaching experience. One fellow teacher mentioned that Grade 6 Music competencies require a teacher who is musically inclined or competent to prevent the subject from becoming a "skip subject." This has inspired the researcher to investigate the competency level of Grade 6 MAPEH teachers and the academic performance of their learners.

The aim is to determine whether there is a correlation between the competency of MAPEH teachers and the academic performance of their students.

Research Questions

This research examined the influence of the competency level of teachers teaching music 6 to the performance of Grade 6 learners. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of music teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. number of years teaching Music 6; and
 - 1.4. seminars and training attended?
2. What is the level of pedagogical competency of MAPEH teachers teaching Music to Grade 6 learners?
3. What is the level of academic performance of Grade 6 learners in terms of test scores in Music?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of pedagogical competency of Music teachers to the performance of Grade 6 learners?
5. Is there a difference in the level of pedagogical competency of Music teachers when grouped according to:
 - 5.1. age;
 - 5.2. sex;
 - 5.3. number of years teaching Music 6; and
 - 5.4. seminars/ training attended?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed the descriptive correlational and causal comparative research designed. It is a type of research method that tests the hypothesis or answers queries of the study. It aims to determine the competency level of 20 MAPEH teachers teaching Music 6 and the competency level of their grade six learners of selected public schools of Loreto North District.

Descriptive correlational research is a type of research design that tries to explain the relationship between two or more variables without making any claims about cause and effect. It includes collecting and analyzing data on at least two variables to see if there is a link between them. In correlational research, the researcher works with only one group of individuals. Instead of comparing two groups, the correlational researcher examines the effect of one or more independent variables on the dependent variable within the same group of subjects.

On the other hand, causal-comparative is a research design that seeks to find relationships between independent and dependent variables after an action or event has already occurred. It is a methodology used to identify cause-effect relationships between independent and dependent variables. Researchers can study cause and effect in retrospect. This can help determine the consequences or causes of differences already existing among or between different groups of people. Additionally, a causal-comparative design is a research design that seeks to find relationships between independent and dependent variables after an action or event has already occurred. The researcher's goal is to determine whether the independent variable affected the outcome, or dependent variable, by comparing two or more groups of individuals ... causal-comparative research [is] also referred to as "ex post facto" research. Moreover, in correlational research, the researcher works with only one group of individuals. Instead of comparing two groups, the correlational researcher examines the effect of one or more independent variables on the dependent variable within the same group of subjects (Lawrence, 2023).

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the 20 MAPEH teachers handling Music 6 subject and their respective grade six learners from the selected public elementary schools of Loreto North District, Municipality of Loreto for School Year 2023-2024. The teacher-respondents will be selected through universal sampling technique.

Both teachers and pupils answered the tool for the independent variable. Table 1 shows the distribution of study respondents.

Table 1. *Respondents of the Study*

<i>Name of Schools</i>	<i>The population of Music 6 Teacher</i>	<i>The population of Grade VI Pupils</i>
Magaud Elementary School	2	67
Jandayugong Elementary School	1	12
Moto Elementary School	1	13
Batohon Elementary School	1	12
D.O. Plaza Elementary School	1	13
Guitas Elementary School	1	18
Loreto Central Elementary School	2	61
Nueva Gracia Elementary School	2	47
Paciencia Elementary School	2	45

Walo Elementary School	1	29
Manawe Elementary School	1	25
Pan-ajatan Elementary School	1	8
Tagbalihaw Elementary School	1	3
Maximo Magadan Elementary School	1	2
Kiawan Elementary School	1	10
Violanta Elementary School	1	17
Total	20	382

Instrument

The instrument used in this study was the research-made questionnaire. The survey questionnaire is composed of questions about the socio-demographic profile of teachers which include age, sex, number of years teaching Music in Grade 6, and seminars/training attended related to Music. To determine the performance task level of grade 6 learners, a 10-item test questions which are MELC-based was also prepared. To correlate the academic performance of Grade 6 pupils to the competency level of their music teacher, a 37-item summative assessment test will be answered by Grade 6 pupils. The summative test is MELC-based and with table of specifications. It was pilot tested to 40 pupils which is not included as respondents of the study. Data gathered was then submitted to statistician for item analysis to test its reliability.

Validation of Instrument

Panels of external and internal validators were assigned to check the instrument before it was administered to the respondents. To test the validity of the instrument, a group of teachers and grade six pupils who were not involved in the study were asked to answer the instrument. Results then was submitted to statistician for reliability test analysis.

Procedure

The following were the data gathering procedures that were employed in this study:

Seeking permission to conduct the study. The researcher wrote a letter of request to the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Agusan del Sur. After it was approved, permission letter was sent to the school heads of selected public schools of Loreto North District to conduct the study. In like manner, the researcher informed the teacher and pupil - respondents who were chosen to answer the survey instrument. Furthermore, the researcher observed proper ethical standards on the conduct of the study and the names of the teacher-respondents were not indicated and any important matters were kept with utmost confidentiality.

Administration and retrieval of the research instrument. The researcher facilitated in the distribution and administration of the survey questionnaire. After which, the retrieval of the research instrument followed and all responses were encoded and stored in the personal computer of the researcher.

Collection and tabulation of data. The researcher collated and tallied all data and submitted it to the statistician for the statistical treatment. Subsequently, the data were subjected to analyses and interpretations.

Data Analysis

The data gathered were compiled, sorted out, organized, and tabulated. These were subjected to a statistical treatment which is regression analysis to facilitate the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data. The following are the statistical tools that were used in this study:

Mean. Frequencies and percentage computation were used to determine the frequency distribution of data at certain levels of ratings. Weighted mean was used to describe the Pedagogical level of competency of Music 6 teachers and the academic performance of the pupils through the class mean score.

Pearson-r. This was used to determine the significant relationship between the pedagogical competency of MAPEH teachers teaching Music and learners academic performance.

Independent T-test - compares the means of two independent groups in order to determine whether there is statistical evidence that the associated population means are significantly different. T-tests are used when the data sets follow a normal distribution and have unknown variances

ANOVA - This was used to determine the significant difference in pedagogical competence when respondents according to age, sex, training attended and teaching experience.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data, which were gathered through the research instrument of the study. It also provides the statistical analysis and the interpretation of data to answer the problem of the study.

Demographic Profile of MAPEH Teachers Teaching Music 6

The table shows the age profile of MAPEH Teachers teaching Music 6

Table 2. Age Profile of the Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage
20-29	6	30 %
30-39	7	35%
40-49	4	20 %
50 and above	3	15 %

Table 2 shows the profile of 20 MAPEH teacher respondents in terms of age. It tells that there were 6 teachers ages 20-29 years old. Likewise, teachers ages 30-39 got the most number with 35 % of the total respondents. Teachers ages 50 and above got the lowest percentage of 15% and followed by level 3 ages 40-49 years old which has a percentage share of 20 % of the total respondents.

Table 3. Profile of the Respondents in terms of Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	3	15%
Female	17	85%

Reflected in Table 3 the respondents profile in terms of sex. It shows that there were 17 female teachers out of 20 respondents. It simply tells that female teachers dominate the number of MAPEH teacher teaching Music 6 in selected public school of Loreto North District.

Table 4. Profile of the Respondents in terms of Experience in Teaching Music 6

Teaching Experience	Frequency	Percentage
9 months	13	65%
10-19 months	3	15 %
21 and above	4	20 %

Table 4 shows the profile of respondent in terms of number of months teaching music in grade 6. It can be glean from the table that there are 13 out of 20 respondent which has 0- 9 months teaching experience. Teachers with 21 months and above noted only 4 while teaching experience within 10-19 months got the lowest frequency of 3.

Table 5. Profile of the Respondents in terms of Seminar and Training Attended

Seminar/Training	Frequency	Percentage
0-19 hours	11	55 %
20-39 hours	5	25 %
40 hours and above	4	20 %

Table 5 reflects the respondents profile in terms of seminar and training attended. It indicates that 11 teacher correspondents which have attended training for 19 hours and below in related to teaching Music. In addition to, there are 5 teachers which attended training and seminars for 20-39 hours. Lastly, only 4 teacher respondents tells that they attended training and seminars for 40 hours and above.

Table 6. Pedagogical Level of Teachers Teaching Music 6

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. I encouraged pupils to listen to music actively and to analyze it, in order to improve their aural skills and their understanding of musical structure.	2.9	Most of the time
2. I used a specific sequence of repertoire and instructional exercises to help students develop their musical skills gradually, with a focus on developing technique and appreciation for music.	2.5	Most of the time
3. I teach using movement, dance, and rhythm to help students develop their musical skills and to help students develop their motor skills, coordination, and musical expression.	2.7	Most of the time
4. I teach specific sequence of melodic exercises and songs, with a focus on developing students' listening and singing skills, in order to help them develop their musical expression and appreciation.	2.8	Most of the time
5. I teach Music that focuses on developing students' listening skills and their ability to interpret musical patterns through movement and body awareness to help students develop their musical expression and performance skills through a range of exercises that involve movement and rhythm.	2.9	Most of the time
6. I let pupils performed singing in front of an audience as a way to practice and apply their musical skills.	2.8	Most of the time
7. I let pupils focus on actively listening to music, analyzing the melodic and rhythmic patterns, and identifying musical elements such as meter, tempo, and form.	2.9	Most of the time
8. I let pupils worked in small groups to perform music, and to work together to achieve a common musical goal.	2.7	Most of the time
9. I let pupils create their own original music, and to use their imagination and creativity to come up with unique musical ideas.	2.7	Most of the time
10. Build students' concentration and focus, as they learn to read and interpret musical notation using	2.5	Most of the time

Solfège and sight reading methods			
11. I teach Music that help pupils develop their musical understanding, as well as their ability to analyze and critique music on a theoretical level.	2.8	Most of the time	
12. I let pupils perform music in front of an audience, either as soloists or in an ensemble.	2.9	Most of the time	
13. I teach Music that helped pupils learned about different musical styles and genres, as well as to access a variety of musical resources for practice and study.	2.8	Most of the time	
14. I teach Music using different instruments in my classroom.	1.8	Sometimes	
Overall Weighted Mean		2.67	Most of the time

As presented in Table 6, statement “I encouraged pupils to listen to music actively and to analyze it, in order to improve their aural skills and their understanding of musical structure, “I teach Music that focuses on developing students' listening skills and their ability to interpret musical patterns through movement and body awareness to help students develop their musical expression and performance skills through a range of exercises that involve movement and rhythm”, “I let pupils focus on actively listening to music, analyzing the melodic and rhythmic patterns, and identifying musical elements such as meter, tempo, and form”, and “I let pupils perform music in front of an audience, either as soloists or in an ensemble” got the highest mean of 2.9 with descriptive rating of “Most of the Time”. Meanwhile, statement “ I teach specific sequence of melodic exercises and songs, with a focus on developing students' listening and singing skills, in order to help them develop their musical expression and appreciation”, “I let pupils focus on actively listening to music, analyzing the melodic and rhythmic patterns, and identifying musical elements such as meter, tempo, and form”, “I teach Music that help pupils develop their musical understanding, as well as their ability to analyze and critique music on a theoretical level”, and “ I teach Music that helped pupils learned about different musical styles and genres”, and “access a variety of musical resources for practice and study” rank next with a mean of 2.8 which has a descriptive rating of “ Most of the Time”. In contrast, statement “I teach Music using different instruments in my classroom” got the lowest mean of 1.8 which tells that teachers do this task in their respective class only “sometimes”. The overall pedagogical competency mean of the respondents is 2.67 which has a descriptive rating of “ most of the time” This explain further that teachers assigned to teach music 6 do the task most of the time to their respective classes.

Table 7. Pupils Performance Task

<i>Pupil's Performance Task</i>		<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>
1.	Respond to beat in Music heard with appropriate conducting patterns.	2.5	Satisfactory
2.	Applied learned concepts of melody.	2.95	Satisfactory
3.	Composes own songs.	2.6	Satisfactory
4.	Performed accurately the designed or structure of a given musical piece.	2.55	Satisfactory
5.	Aurally determined the sound of a single instrument in any section of an orchestra.	2.8	Satisfactory
6.	Applies the appropriate dynamics level in vocal or instrumental music.	2.7	Satisfactory
7.	Performed songs with different texture.	2.75	Satisfactory
8.	Performed songs with different tempo marks.	2.8	Satisfactory
9.	Demonstrate harmony in group singing performance.	2.4	Satisfactory
10.	Accompany songs using any musical instruments.	1.9	Needs improvement
Over all Weighted Mean		2.6	Satisfactory

Table 7 shows the pupils performance task in Music 6. Statement “ Applied learned concepts of melody” has a mean of 2.95 with descriptive rating of “ Satisfactory” got the highest mean. It was followed by statement “ Aurally determined the sound of a single instrument in any section of an orchestra”and“ Performed songs with different tempo marks” got a mean of 2.8 with descriptive rating of “ Satisfactory”. Moreover, “ “Performed songs with different texture” has a mean of 2.75 with descriptive rating of “Satisfactory” Most of the task presented on the table was done satisfactorily by most of the grade 6 respondents. Furthermore, “ accompany songs using any musical instruments”which has a mean of 1.9 with a descriptive rating of “ Needs Improvement” is the most least learned competency. It further tells that only 50% to 59% of the respondents can play any musical instruments in school. This results correlates to the result of pedagogical competence of teachers as stated in table 6 item 14 which tells that teacher only “sometime” play instruments in their respective class.

Table 8. Class Academic Performance

<i>Teacher Respondents</i>	<i>Class MPS</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Equivalent Grade</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>
1	34.02	12.59	74	Not Meet Expectation
2	62.28	23.04	84	Very Satisfactory
3	61.3	22.68	83	Satisfactory
4	40.62	15.03	75	Fairly Satisfactory
5	26.35	9.75	70	Not Meet Expectation
6	34.51	12.77	73	Not Meet Expectation
7	24.74	9.15	69	Not Meet Expectation
8	27.75	10.3	71	Not Meet Expectation
9	34.10	12.62	73	Not Meet Expectation
10	64.08	23.71	84	Satisfactory
11	57.93	21.43	82	Satisfactory
12	34.18	12.65	73	Not Meet Expectation

13	73.19	27.08	88	Very Satisfactory
14	69.48	25.75	87	Very Satisfactory
15	56.49	20.9	82	Satisfactory
16	55.37	20.40	81	Satisfactory
17	59.31	21.94	83	Satisfactory
18	43.92	16.25	77	Fairly Satisfactory
19	37.84	14	74	Not Meet Expectation
20	41.89	15.5	76	Fairly Satisfactory
Over all Mean	46.9675	17.38	77.95	Fairly Satisfactory

Table 8 presents the class academic performance of grade six learners. It shows that 8 out of 20 class respondents belongs to category “below proficiency level” which rate below 74% with a descriptive rating of :” Did not Meet Expectation”. On the other hand, 2 out of 20 class respondents got a descriptive rating of “ Fairly Satisfactory” while 6 class respondents rates as “ Satisfactory”. Moreover, 4 out of 20 class respondents rated as” Very Satisfactory”. The overall weighted responses is rated as “ Fairly Satisfactory” with equivalent grade of 77.95 respectively.

Significant relationship between the level of Pedagogical Competency of MAPEH Teachers to the Performance in music of Grade 6 learners

The table below shows the correlation analysis between the level of pedagogical competency of MAPEH teachers to the performance in music of Grade 6 learners.

Table 9. Correlation Analysis between the level of Pedagogical Competency of MAPEH teachers to the Academic Performance in music of Grade 6 learners

Variables	R	value
Pedagogical Competency	0.506	0.023
Academic Performance		

Table 9 shows the result of the correlation analysis between pedagogical competency of MAPEH teachers to the academic performance in music of Grade 6 learners. It can be gleaned from the data that the pedagogical competency of teachers greatly affect to the performance of learners. This is the evidence of the r-values which is .506 and its p-value of 0.023 respectively.

Table 10. Difference in the Level of Pedagogical Competency of MAPEH Teachers when Group According to Age

Variables	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	Frequency	Percentage
Age	.530	3	0.177	0.516
Respondents	5.478	16	0.342	0.677

The table above shows the difference in the level of pedagogical competency of MAPEH Teachers when group according to age. It further tells that the pedagogical competence does not vary when respondents are grouped according to age.

Table 11. Difference in the Level of Pedagogical Competency of MAPEH Teachers when Group according to Sex

Independent Sample T- Test			
Pedagogical Competency	t	df	P
	.130	18	.898

Table 11 reflects the difference in the level of pedagogical competency of MAPEH Teachers when group according to sex were the t- is 0.130 and the p-value is 0.898. It finds out that the pedagogical competence of MAPEH teachers do not vary when respondents are grouped according to sex.

Table 12. Difference in the Level of Pedagogical Competency of MAPEH Teachers when Group according to Teaching Experience

Variables	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	Frequency	Percentage
Age	.436	2	0.218	0.665	0.527
Respondents	5.572	12	0.328	0.342	

Table 12 shows the difference in the level of pedagogical competency of MAPEH Teachers when group according to teaching experience. It shows that the pedagogical competence do not vary when respondents are grouped according to teaching experience.

Table 13 present data about the difference in the level of pedagogical competency of MAPEH teachers when group according to seminars/ training attended. Level 2 has a mean difference of .224 and has a p-value of .671. It further shows that there is a significant difference in pedagogical competence when respondents are grouped according to training attended. It can be interpreted that teachers who attended training or seminars are more competent in teaching.

Table 13. *The difference in the Level of Pedagogical Competency of MAPEH Teachers when Group according to Seminars/ Trainings Attended*

	<i>Mean Difference</i>	<i>Seminar</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
2	.224	.260	.861	.671
3	.839	.281	-2.982	.022
3	.615	.323	-1.903	.168

Demographic Profile of MAPEH Teachers in Terms of Age. Most of the teachers that handle music to grade six learners ages from 30-39 years old of the total respondents. In contrast, teachers ages 50 years old and above got a lowest percentage. The data further tells that most teachers assigned in teaching Music to grade six learners are in their middle age of their teaching career.

Demographic Profile of MAPEH Teachers in Terms of Sex. Survey revealed that there were more female teachers in the field of teaching compare to male in the field of Loreto North District. This further tells that there are more women in the field of education than male.

Demographic Profile of MAPEH Teachers in Terms of Teaching Experience. Most of the respondents teach the subject for less than 19 months. . Based on the survey, it can be analyzed that Almost MAPEH Teachers teaching Music to grade six learners in the public school of Loreto North District has less than two years teaching experience in Music 6.

Demographic Profile of MAPEH Teachers in Terms of Seminar/Training Attended. Survey says that almost teacher respondents have attended seminar/ training for 19 hours and below in related to teaching Music . Lastly, only few among them teacher respondents tells that they attended training and seminars for 40 hours and above. This emphasized that most MAPEH teachers assigned in grade six has less seminar/training attended.

Pedagogical Competency of MAPEH Teachers Teaching Music 6. Most statement mention as pedagogical competency in the survey questionnaires has a descriptive rating of “Most of the Time”. This explain further that teachers assigned to teach music 6 do the task most of the time to their respective classes.

Statement “I encouraged pupils to listen to music actively and to analyze it, in order to improve their aural skills and their understanding of musical structure, “I teach Music that focuses on developing students' listening skills and their ability to interpret musical patterns through movement and body awareness to help students develop their musical expression and performance skills through a range of exercises that involve movement and rhythm”, “I let pupils focus on actively listening to music, analyzing the melodic and rhythmic patterns, and identifying musical elements such as meter, tempo, and form”, and “I let pupils perform music in front of an audience, either as soloists or in an ensemble” got the highest mean with descriptive rating of “Most of the Time”.

Meanwhile, statement “ I teach specific sequence of melodic exercises and songs, with a focus on developing students' listening and singing skills, in order to help them develop their musical expression and appreciation”, “I let pupils focus on actively listening to music, analyzing the melodic and rhythmic patterns, and identifying musical elements such as meter, tempo, and form”, “I teach Music that help pupils develop their musical understanding, as well as their ability to analyze and critique music on a theoretical level”, and “ I teach Music that helped pupils learned about different musical styles and genres”, and “access a variety of musical resources for practice and study” rank next which has a descriptive rating of “ Most of the Time”.

In contrast, statement “I teach Music using different instruments in my classroom” got the lowest mean which tells that teachers do this task in their respective class only “sometimes”.

Robert Adams commented that teachers have accepted the playing of instruments in general music class as a normal part of instruction. In other words, we don't teach a child to play a recorder, or xylophone, or what have you so that they can play an instrument instead, we teach a child to play a musical instrument because that is the best way for him or her to learn to improvise, convey expressive intent, generate musical ideas, and so forth. The stipulation of learning varied repertoire is still valuable, so children also learn to play musical instruments in order to fully experience a repertoire of instrumental music. The goal is not to be able to play an instrument, it is to use playing an instrument as a means to learning music. (2017)

Pupils Performance Task Results. The performance task statement “ Applied learned concepts of melody” . It was followed by statement “ Aurally determined the sound of a single instrument in any section of an orchestra ”and“ Performed songs with different tempo marks” has a descriptive rating of “ Satisfactory”.

Moreover, “ “Performed songs with different texture” has a with descriptive rating of “Satisfactory” Most of the task presented on the table was done satisfactorily by most of the grade 6 respondents.

Furthermore, “accompany songs using any musical instruments” with a descriptive rating of “ Needs Improvement” is the most least learned competency. This results correlates to the result of pedagogical competence of teachers as stated in table 6 item 14 which tells that teacher only “sometime” play instruments in their respective class.

As cited by Samillano (2007) revealed that most of the teachers who are non-MAPEH specialist or non-MAPEH major graduates had problems in teaching the subject because of lack of facilities, equipment and instructional materials.

Class Academic Performance

Survey says that most class respondents got below proficiency level which has a descriptive rating of :” Did not Meet Expectation”. On the other hand, only few class respondents got a descriptive rating of “ Fairly Satisfactory” The overall weighted responses is rated as “ Fairly Satisfactory”.

Correlation Analysis between the Level of Pedagogical Competency of MAPEH Teachers to the Academic Performance in Music of Grade 6 learners. The result of the correlation analysis between pedagogical competency of MAPEH teachers to the Academic Performance in music of Grade 6 learners has the r-values of more than to the margin of error and have less than p-value. It can be glean from the data that the pedagogical competency of teachers greatly affect to the performance of learners. . Thus the null hypothesis is rejected with respect to the profile variables.

This finding supported by Yuli Sudargini and Agus Porwanto as they declare that the success of the educational process is determined by the teacher which is an important component in achieving educational goals, (2020).

According to Asbari (2020) teachers are professional educators of scientists with the main task transforming, developing, and disseminating science, technology and arts through education, research, and community service ”.. The teacher plays a major role in education development in particular formal education on campus. Teacher t greatly determines the success of students, especially in relation to the learning process teach.

The importance of a teacher having pedagogical competence is that teachers can develop their students' abilities maximally because teachers who master several theories about education by understanding various educational theories can choose which one is the best to help the development of students. In addition, the teacher is also expected to understand various learning models. By increasingly understanding the many learning models, it will be easier for him to teach children according to the situation of their students. Basically, increasing the pedagogic competence of teachers will prevent monotonous learning activities, dislike students and make students lose their interest and absorption and concentration of learning.

The difference in the level of Pedagogical Competency of MAPEH Teachers when group according to age, sex, teaching experience and to seminars/ training attended. The p-value of .pedagogical competency when group according to teaching experience and training/seminar attended is more than to the margin of error. This means that that there is a significant difference in pedagogical competence when respondents are grouped according to training attended. It can be interpreted further that teachers who attended training or seminars are more competent in teaching compares to those who haven't attended seminars.

Voster (2007) emphasized in his research that “Primary school teachers are failing to meet a requirement of the national curriculum because they lack the skills to teach music.

Seminars and training's help teachers to gain new insights, enhance their skills and potentials. It also give teachers a chance to showcase their new discovered teaching techniques for others to benchmark with. Seminars also serves as an avenue to learn new strategy and competency for teachers to uplift their pedagogical competency in teaching the subject they are teaching.

Conclusions

It can be concluded that factors explored and determined in this study like pedagogical competency of teachers, length of teaching experience and seminars or training attended by teachers significantly affect the academic performance of pupils in learning Music. On the other hand, there is no difference in the level of pedagogical competency of MAPEH Teachers to the Academic Performance of Grade Six Learners when group according to age and sex.

The researcher recommends that teachers motivate students to develop good study habits and a sense of responsibility in their learning. Teachers should also familiarize themselves with the competency-based music education curriculum and enhance their self-study and learning skills to better fulfill their responsibilities, including tasks outlined in the MELC. Additionally, teachers should create alternative instructional designs using developed materials tailored to students' needs. School heads are encouraged to fully support teachers by organizing seminars and workshops for skill enhancement, while administrators should invest in musical instruments for hands-on learning. Finally, future researchers are advised to explore additional factors influencing learners' academic performance in music.

References

- Adams, R. (2017) Mister a Music Place "Where Music Teacher Gather" <https://mramusicplace.net/2017/02/22/why-teach-instruments-in-general-music/>
- Ahmed, K, (2020) The Importance of Music in School: Why Music Education Matters <https://stagemusiccenter.com/music-school-blog-winchester-acton-ma/2022/8/7/the-importance-of-music-in-school-why-music-education-matters>
- Bautista, A. (2022) Full article: Music in early childhood teacher education Taylor & Francis Online <https://www.tandfonline.com>
- Brussels, 1953 [2] International Conference on the Role and Place of Music in the Education of Youth and Adults

<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/search/N-EXPLORE-e2efe0f1-59e7-4ddd-b82f-ca2e53896f6a>

Chung, F. (2022) Conclusions and Implications: Toward a Conceptual Framework for Music Teacher Education. DOI:10.1007/978-981-19-5033-9_7 In book: Music and Play in Early Childhood Education (pp.201-229) Publisher: Springer Nature

Concina, E (2023) Effective Music Teachers and Effective Music Teaching Today: A Systematic Review DOI:10.3390/educsci13020107

Guadalupe, J. T. (2023). Enacting Music Curriculum Contextualization in the Philippine. Philippine Journal of Education Studies.

Guadalupe, J. T. (2023). Enacting Music Curriculum Contextualization in the Philippines Philippine Journal of Education Studies, 140

Guadalupe, J et al. (2023) Enacting Music Curriculum Contextualization in the Philippine K to 12 Curriculum: Negotiations, Constraints, and Mediating Forces Philippine Journal of Education Studies Volume 1, Issue 1 (2023), pp. 11-36 Website: <http://educ.upd.edu.ph> <https://doi.org/10.61839/29848180j7e8c7>

Hayes, A. (2023) T-Test: What It Is With Multiple Formulas and When To Use Them [https://www.investopedia.com/terms/t/t-test.asp#:~:text=Error%20Code%3A%20100013\)-What%20Is%20a%20T%20Test%3F,flipping%20a%20coin%20100%20times](https://www.investopedia.com/terms/t/t-test.asp#:~:text=Error%20Code%3A%20100013)-What%20Is%20a%20T%20Test%3F,flipping%20a%20coin%20100%20times)

How Music Education Helps Students Learn, Achieve, and Succeed <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED541070.pdf>

Huang, Y. (2023) What Is the Purpose of Primary School Music Education? Source: Research and Advances in Education ISSN 2788-7057 FEB. 2023 VOL.2, NO.223 doi:10.56397/RAE.2023.02.02 <https://www.paradigmpress.org/rae/article/view/421>

Jaschke, A. (2018) Music Lessons Improve Children's Cognitive Skills And Academic Performance <https://www.frontiersin.org/news/2018/04/19/neuroscience-music-lessons-cognitive-skills-academic-performance>

Jing, Y. (2023) The Impact of Music Education on Students' Academic Performance and Academic Motivation: A Quantitative Study DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10021657>

Juraschka, R. (2021) Competency-Based Education: What It Is and 6 Main Principles to Use at School <https://www.prodigygame.com/main-en/blog/competency-based-education/>

Lawrence, F. (2023) Research Methodology Group UOPX Research Community Causal-Comparative Research <https://www.phoenix.edu/content/dam/edu/research/doc/2023/causal-comparative-research.pdf>

Music Education Matters to Cognitive Development (2022) <https://degree.lamar.edu/online-programs/education/master-music-education/music-education-matters-to-cognitive-development/>

Nnenna, U. (2023) The Impact Of Music Education On Cognitive Development And Academic Achievement In Adolescents https://www.researchgate.net/publication/370678665_The_impact_of_music_education_on_cognitive_development_and_academic_achievement_in_adolescents

Paglusch, T. (2017). What is Music? Music Defined by Musicians. Music House. <https://www.musichouseschool.com/what-is-music-music-defined-by-musicians>

Rajesh, R., & Joseph, Z. C. (2023) Competency-based teacher education (CBTE): A training module to improve knowledge, attitude, and practices (KAP) of school teachers on learning disabilities in children. J Family Med Prim Care. 2023 May;12(5):874-880. doi: 10.4103/jfmpc.jfmpc_580_22. Epub 2023 May 31. PMID: 37448921; PMCID: PMC10336952.

Rozimurodov (2024) Musical Performance Skills Of A Future Music Teacher As A Pedagogical Problem <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/musical-performance-skills-of-a-future-music-teacher-as-a-pedagogical-problem>

Silvestre, M. (2020) Lived Experiences of Teachers Teaching Music, Arts, Physical Education and Health: Implications to Graduate Education <https://ijisrt.com/assets/upload/files/IJISRT20DEC053.pdf>

Sudargini, Y. & Purwanto, A. (2020) The Effect Of Teachers Pedagogic Competency On The Learning Outcomes Of Students Journal Of Industrial Engineering & Management Research (JIEMAR) Vol. 1 No. 4: DEC 2020 ISSN ONLINE: 2722 – 8878 <http://www.jiemar.org> DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7777/jiemar>

Sun, J. (2022) Exploring the Impact of Music Education on the Psychological and Academic Outcomes of Students: Mediating Role of Self-Efficacy and self-esteem <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/psychology/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.841204/full>

Taboada, A. et al. (2023) Voices from the Classroom: Understanding the Challenges Faced by Teachers in Teaching Music, Arts, Physical Education and Health in the Division of Toledo City <https://inter-publishing.com/index.php/IJISE/article/view/1805/1559>

Welch & Henley (2014) Addressing The Challenges Of Teaching Music By Generalist Primary School Teachers <http://www.abemeducacaomusical.com.br/revistas/revistaabem/index.php/revistaabem/article/viewFile/459/383>

What Is Competency-Based Education? <https://aurora-institute.org/our-work/competencyworks/competency-based-education/>

Wells, A. (2022) 10 Things You Can Do To Improve Students Performance <https://blog.schoolmint.com/10-things-you-can-do-to-improve-student-performance>

Vu, T., Magis-Weinberg, L., Jansen, B. R., van Atteveldt, N., Janssen, T. W., Lee, N. C., & Meeter, M. (2022). Motivation-achievement cycles in learning: A literature review and research agenda. *Educational Psychology Review*, 34(1), 39-71.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Rosalie D. Magallanes, MAEL.ED

Sto. Tomas Elementary School

Department of Education – Philippines

Roel P. Villocino, PhD

Assumption College of Nabunturan – Philippines